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Time and Cost Performance Status of Sikta Irrigation Contract

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Abstract: Government of Nepal (GoN) is implementing many small, medium and large type of Irrigation Projects. Sikta Irrigation Project (SIP) is the National Pride Project implemented by the GoN. The command area of the project has 42766.00 ha and beneficiary of the project have 46715 house hold consisting 449588 population of Banke district.

The study is focused to analyses the contractual performance of SIP using Earn Value Analysis for ongoing and status assessment of completed contracts along with the consequences of delay and disputes of selected contracts. The project consists of 52 no of contracts out of which 14 ongoing contracts were evaluated using EVA & S-curve.

It is found that trough the contracts were within budget, however the time overrun has server. The average cost variance percentage 2.24%, Cost performance index 1.02, shows the effectiveness of cost in the project due to low bedding of 86% of contracts. schedule variance percentage is -44.2%, Schedule performance index is 0.55 and average index is 0.785 where less then 1.0. Depending upon condition the estimate to complete and estimate at completion may vary from 1.95 million to 3.54 million and 3.78 million to 5.37 million respectively.

Keywords: Earn Value Analysis , S-curve, Estimate to Complete, Estimate at Completion, SV

1. Background

The success of any construction project is measured in terns of its performance on schedule, cost, quality and no-dispute with safety. The project performance is measured base on timely completion, within the budget, required quality standards and customers satisfaction (Maskey and Mishra,2018). As a consequence of poor performance, the

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projects mainly face the problem of time overrun and cost overrun. Mishra and Chaudhary (2018) mentioned that for productivity during operation its significant to reduce fixed cost during construction through effective material management , schedule management, labour and equipment assuring quality. Lets analyse the performance with a case of , Sikta Irrigation Project which is located at the Banke district of Nepal whose water source is West Rapti Rive. There are two system of canal i.e., Eastern canal command area 9000ha and western canal command area 33766 ha. When project have been completed then beneficiary of the project have 46715 house hold and 449588 population of Banke district. Poverty, illiteracy etc. are seen in Banke district, where Sikta Irrigation Project is under construction. The source of cash income of the local people in this area is mainly the sale of grain. The production will be increased and living standard of the farmers in Banke district will be enhanced by operating the project. A major challenge of the project is the dispersive soil structure in the canal. The failure of canal at the time of trail testing is an example of technical problem. The dispersive soil is observed where the canal and other structures were constructed.

2. Statement of the problem

Sikta Irrigation project of command area 42766 ha and beneficiary of the project have 46715 house hold and 449588 population of Banke district (SIP, DPR 2014). The delay of project might affect agriculture productivity. A country like Nepal where food security and food severancy is big issue need to focus on its agricultural development, on agricultural infrastructure. In this circumstance this project it self is unique one to increase the yield of agriculture product in the area to overcome starvation significantly in the respected area that's why the project should have been completed on time with accepted quality within the budget without any safety or ethically issues so the researcher has attempt to conduct the study and contractual performance assessment of Sikta Irrigation Project.

Sikta Irrigation Project was started 2004/2005 (*B.S.2061/062*) with an objective to complete by 2019/2020 (*B.S.2076/077*) however the project has not completed yet so its performance need to be study and issue related performance should be accessed so the researcher as made an attempt to contine to conduct an area.

3. Objective of the study

The main aim of the research is to analyze the performance of ongoing contracts using Earn Value Analysis through S-curve.

4. Literature Review

Construction Projects Performance

Construction project performance is always a matter of great concern as it is operated with huge investment and most of tax payer amount get utilized in construction as government is main player. All most all big projects are in hand of government. Media attention is high

to the sector. It needs continuous project performance assessment still how a project like sikta irrigation whose significance is such may be poor performing need to be studied. So Earn value analysis and S- Curve has been reviewed.

Earn Value Analysis

Earn value assess where we are ?, Where we were supposed to be? How to correct the project to reach again? (Mishra & Bhandari, ...)it is an approach to find how , where and how much we get deviated from the target for taking corrective action(Mishra and Bhandari.... It is an evaluation of difference based on pre decided targets through measure of each activities value of work.

The Planned Value (PV), (budgeted cost of work scheduled or BCWS)-the baseline cost assumed to be utilized during the planned time for the said activity.

The Actual Cost (AC), (the actual cost of work performed or ACWP)-the real costs for doing activity of the work in the period.

The Earned Value (EV), (the budget cost of work performed or BCWP)-the real value obtained by doing the activity of the work actually done.

The values evaluate the difference between plan and action of the project and expressed as Cost variance (CV) as earned work against actual portion of budget utilized. the negative, zero and positive variance reflect the over budget, on budget and under budget condition of the project respectively. i.e, $(CV) = EV - AC$

Where as $CV \% (CV \%) = CV / EV$

Similarly, Schedule Variance (SV) express time performance of project as cost variance represents budget performance. The negative, zero and positive value of schedule variance reflect behind , on decided and ahead of schedule conditions of project.

$(SV) = EA - PV$

$(SV \%) = SV / PV$

Avoid the negative should be our attempt.

Schedule Performance Index (SPI) express the efficiency of on going project by using index value and comparing with standard 1. SPI equal or greater than 1, express the good performance as it is either on or ahead of schedule in condition of less than 1, implies the need of performance improvement as its lacking in response to planned. Even project crashing might be an option if cost allows.

Schedule Performance Index = EV / PV

Cost Performance Index (CPI) express cost efficiency after comparing with 1 as standard to maintain at zero or greater than 1 for keeping project as expected or under budgeted while less than 1, the project needs improvement in turms of budget being over budget.

$$\text{Cost Performance Index} = \text{EV} / \text{AC}$$

The widely used graph for quick understanding is given below (Dummies-A wiley brand, 2014).

Figure 1: Earned Value Analysis- as S Curve

5. Methodology

Study Area

Sikta Irrigation Project is the National Pride Project, it is located at the Banke District with perennial source. There are two system of canal i.e., Eastern canal and Western canal. Eastern canal passes through Rapti Sonari Gaupalika and Narainapur Gaupalika its length 53.50 km and command area 9000 ha .There are 11 no's of secondary canal. Among them Rajkulo contains S1,S2,S3,S4 and Phattepur contains S5,S6,S7,S8,S8,S9,S10,S11. The length of secondary and tertiary canal is 145 km. The discharge of Eastern canal 14 cumec. Western canal passes through Rapti Sonari Gaupalika, Dudwa Gaupalika, Kohalpur Nagarpalika and Baijnath Gaupalika. Its length is 45.25 km with trapezoidal canal section having the tail escape at the end and command area 33766 km. The discharge of western canal 50 cumec. There are 7 no's of secondary canal. S1(Sidhaniya branch), Dunduwa,S2(Gohawa), S3(Akalgherwa), S4(Persenpur), S5(Pidari), S6(GaruwaGaun) are the secondary canal. The length of secondary and tertiary canal 233 km. The ideal length of canal is 30 km. The bed slope of canal is 1/7000. when project have been completed then beneficiary of the project have 46715 house hold and 449588 population of Banke district.

Sikta, which started construction 14 years ago in magh 2063. It was supposed to be built at an average cost of Rs 12 billion. Five years after scheduled time, the project has started partially providing water to the farmers. The estimated cost of the project in the initial year 2061/062 was 12.80 billion. Later second revision and add scope of work the approved total financial cost of whole Project was NRS. 25.02 billion in fiscal year 2071/72. However, the cost of the Project has been increased to NRs 39.98 billion due to

rectification of right main canal, some additional command area development and command area protection works, increased cost of Left main canal as per contract agreement, increased cost of Dunduwa irrigation system as per DPR, social cost to address social requirements of project affected area, increased cost of land acquisition, and inflation.

(Source: SIP DPR, 2014)
 Figure 2: Sikta Irrigation Project Layout Map.

Secondary Data

Secondary data will be obtained from previous research works relevant to the thesis topic like various fact findings on Irrigation project. Also the important source for the secondary data will be Sikta Irrigation Project Office. Various other organizations will also be the source of the secondary data.

6. Data Analysis

The Earned value analysis and S Curve are used as analysis technique to assess variation of time and cost, Estimate to completion and Estimate at completion.

Data plotted in Ms excel to analyze the Earn Value and drawn the S-Curve of the project .

Table 1 : Project Performance definition and Earned Value Analysis Formulas.

S.N	Particulars	Abbrev.	Description	Formule	Interpretation of Result
1	Budget at Completion	BAC	Baseline project cost		
2	Actual Cost /Actual Cost of Work Performance	AC (ACWP)	Total costs incurred in completing work during a given period		

S.N	Particulars	Abbrev.	Description	Formule	Interpretation of Result
3	Earned Value/Budgeted cost of Work performed	EV (BCWP)	Physical work completed during a given period		
4	Planned Value/ Budgeted cost of work schedule	PV (BCWS)	Physical work schedule for completion during a given period		
5	Cost Variance	CV	Cost overrun during a given period	EV-AC	Positive = Under planned cost
					Negative = on planned cost
					Negative = Over planned cost
6	Cost Performance Index	CPI	Cost efficiency ratio	EV/AC	Greater than 1.0=Under lplanned cost
					Exactly 1.0= On planned cost
					Less than 1= Over planned cost
7	Schedul Variance	SV	Schedule slipped during a given period	EV-PV	Positive = Ahead of schedule
					Negative = on schedule
					Negative = Behind schedule
8	Schedule Performance Index	SPI	Schedule efficiency ratio	EV/PV	Greater than 1.0=Ahead of Schedule
					Exactly 1.0= On schedule
					Less than 1= Behind schedule
9	Estimate to Completion	ETC	Expected additional cost needed	EAC-AC	
10	Estimate to Completion	EAC	Expected total cost	BAC/CPI	
11	Variance at Completion	VAC	Estimated cost overrun at end	BAC-EAC	Positive = Under planned cost
					Negative = on planned cost
					Negative = Over

					planned cost
12	Status	n/a	Average of CPI and SPI	$(CPI+SPI)/2$	
			Status color key		
			GREEN=on track	1	
			YELLOW = Slightly behind schedule/budget	0.85 but < 1.0	
			RED=Needs immediate attention	< 0.85	

(Source : 5. Haughey, (2015); Mishra and Bhandari, 2018)

Table 2 : Estimate At Completion (EAC) & Estimate To Complete (ETC)

	EAC	ETC
If there's no variance at all	BAC	EAC - AC
If there is variance and it is expected to continue	BAC/CPI	BAC/CPI - AC
If there was variance, but now it's gone	AC + BAC - EV	BAC - EV
If your original estimates are fundamentally flawed	AC + new ETC	new bottom-up estimate
If you are over budget and past due	$[(BAC - EV) / (CPI * SPI)] + AC$	$[(BAC - EV) / (CPI * SPI)]$

Additional Cost Formulas

- $(EV/BAC)*100\% = \% \text{ complete}$
- Variance at Completion = $VAC = BAC - EAC$
- To-Complete Performance Index (TCPI) based on BAC = $(BAC - EV)/(BAC - AC)$
- TCPI based on EAC = $(BAC - EV)/(EAC - AC)$

Source: (PPM; Mishra and Bhandari, 2018)

7. Result and Discussion

Performance Assesment of Ongoing Contracts.

The project documents reveal that the contract amount for SIP/EMC/ICB-01 has highest value totaling NRS 3069859 thousand followed by SIP/SBC/NCB-02 and so on. Command area protection work of SIP/CAP/NCB-12 is the project with least contract amount NRs13072 thousands. Baed on planned start date and finished date the project has not been completed in planned schedule time and 14 out of 13 projects has time extension. Only one project has not time extension till now. Minimum 6 month(one time) time

extension of five projects and maximum time extension of project has 53 month (four times) i.e., SIP/SBC/NCB-02 (Pratibedan (2076)).

The planned value is far more than the earned values for all the projects which shows the slow the progress of the work. Furthermore earned value for the project more than actual value of the project which indicates that the projects are within the budget. The Earned Value Analysis (EVA) using table 3 has been shown on table 4 along with interpretation in upcoming Sections.

Table 3: Project Performance status

Actual Start Date	Planned					Contract Amount (In thousand NRs)	Contract No
	Planned Value (PV)	% Complete	Duration(Month)	Completion Date	Start Date		
24-Jul-17	268740	87.5	28	11-Nov-19	24-Jul-17	3069859.0	SIP/EMC/ICB-01
12-Jun-14	84110	79.7	25	04-Jul-16	12-Jun-14	105469.00	SIP/SBC/NCB-02
21-Jun-17	39340	97.9	13	18-Jul-18	21-Jun-17	40192.00	SIP/CAP/NCB-04
04-Jun-18	11810	90.3	14	10-Apr-19	04-Jun-18	13072.00	SIP/CAP/NCB-12
06-Jun-18	16470	87	12	05-Jul-19	06-Jul-18	18934.00	SIP/CAP/NCB-15(Re)
05-Jul-18	81540	96.4	12	05-Jul-19	05-Jul-18	84561.00	SIP/CAP/NCB-16
02-Jul-18	69223	97.3	11	05-Jul-19	02-Jul-18	71173.00	SIP//DR/NCB-01
02-Jul-18	64246	83.3	24	05-Jul-19	02-Jul-18	77096.00	SIP//DR/NCB-02
03-Jul-18	66825	87.1	24	05-Jul-20	03-Jul-18	76726.00	SIP/RMC/AK/L/NCB-01
03-Jul-18	60095	87.1	24	05-Jul-20	03-Jul-18	69000.00	SIP/RMC/GH/W/NCB-01
03-Jul-18	59347	80.7	24	05-Jul-20	03-Jul-18	73585.00	SIP/RMC/PR/S/NCB-01
03-Jul-18	63780	83.9	24	05-Jul-20	03-Jul-18	76058.00	SIP/RMC/PD/R/NCB-01
19-May-19	25790	80	12	18-May-20	19-May-19	32254.00	SIP/SBC/NCB-04
16-Feb-20	29148	53.9	12	22-Feb-21	16-Feb-20	54128.00	SIP/DIS/NCB-01/076-077

Finished date	11-Nov-20	04-Dec-20	18-Oct-20	10-Dec-20	3005-Jan-21	05-Oct-20	05-Oct-20	02-Dec-20	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	1805-Jan-21	22-Feb-20
Duration(Month)	42	78	39	34	3005-Jan-21	27	26	41	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	3005-Jan-21	1805-Jan-21	12

Contract No		Actual			EOT I(Month)	EoT II (Month)	EoT III(Month)	EOT IV(month)
		Actual Value (AV)	Earned Value(EV)	% Complete				
SIP/EMC/ICB-01		1493900.00	1523800.00	48.7	14			
SIP/SBC/NCB-02		70100.00	71100.00	66.5	12	24	5	
SIP/CAP/NCB-04		19300.00	24100.00	48	6			
SIP/CAP/NCB-12		5739.00	6010.00	43.9	6	8	6	
SIP/CAP/NCB-15(Re)		7745.00	7866.00	40.9	6	3	6	
SIP/CAP/NCB-16		24753.00	25200.00	29.3	3	3		
SIP//DR/NCB-01		58738.00	59088.00	82.5	6	9		
SIP//DR/NCB-02		34083.00	34623.00	44.2	3	8	6	
SIP/RMC/AKL/NCB-01		31849.00	32200.00	41.5	6			
SIP/RMC/GHW/NCB-01		34042.00	34420.00	49.3	6			
SIP/RMC/PRS/NCB-01		21144.00	21684.00	28.7	6			
SIP/RMC/PDR/NCB-01		10223.00	10570.00	13.4	6			
SIP/SBC/NCB-04		5890.00	6350.00	18.3	6			
SIP/DIS/NCB-01/076-077		14619.00	15580.00	27				

Table 4: Earned Value Analysis

	Item Description	OVERALL	SIP/EMC/ICB-01	SIP/SBC/NC B-02	SIP/CAP/NC B-04	SIP/CAP/NC B-12	SIP/CAP/NC B-15(Re)	SIP/CAP/NC B-16	SIP//DR/NCB-01	SIP//DR/NCB-02	SIP/RMC/AK L/NCB-01	SIP/RMC/GH W/NCB-01	SIP/RMC/PR S/NCB-01	SIP/RMC/PD R/NCB-01	SIP/SBC/NC B-04	SIP/DIS/NCB-01/076-077
Budget	Over all BAC	3862107.00	3069859.00	105469.00	40192.00	13072.00	18934.00	84561.00	71173.00	77096.00	76726.00	69000.00	73585.00	76058.00	32254.00	54128.00
	PV	3359124.00	2687400.00	84110.00	39340.00	11810.00	16470.00	81540.00	69223.00	64246.00	66825.00	60095.00	59347.00	63780.00	25790.00	29148.00
Earned	EV	1874145.00	1523800.00	71100.00	24100.00	6010.00	7866.00	25200.00	59088.00	34623.00	32200.00	34420.00	21684.00	10570.00	6350.00	17134.00
Actual	AC	1832125.00	1493900.00	70100.00	19300.00	5739.00	7745.00	24753.00	58738.00	34083.00	31849.00	34042.00	21144.00	10223.00	5890.00	14619.00
Cost	CV	42020.00	29900.00	1000.00	4800.00	271.00	121.00	447.00	350.00	540.00	351.00	378.00	540.00	347.00	460.00	2515.00

Schedule	SV%	SV	CV%
	-44.2	-1484979	2.24
-43.29	-1163600	1.96	
-15.46	-13010	1.4	
-38.73	-15240	19.91	
-49.11	-5800	4.5	
-52.24	-8604	1.53	
-69.09	-56340	1.77	
-14.64	-10135	0.59	
-46.1	-29623	1.55	
-51.81	-34625	1.09	
-42.72	-25675	1.09	
-63.46	-37663	2.49	
-83.42	-53210	3.28	
-75.37	-19440	7.24	
-41.21	-12014	14.67	

		Item Description	
Performance Index	CPI		
	SPI	0.55	1.0
If there's no variance at all	ETC	2029982.00	1.0
	EAC	3862107.00	1.0
If there is variance and it is expected to continue	ETC	1954254.41	0.56
	EAC	3786379.41	1.0
		SIP/EMC/ICB-	
		SIP/SBC/NCB-	
		SIP/CAP/NCB-	
		SIP/DR/NCB-	
		SIP/DR/NCB-	
		SIP/RMC/AKL/NCB-01	
		SIP/RMC/GHW/NCB-01	
		SIP/RMC/PRS/NCB-01	
		SIP/RMC/PDR/NCB-01	
		SIP/SBC/NCB-	
		SIP/DIS/NCB-	

If there was variance, but now it's gone	EAC	ETC
	3820087.00	1987962.00
3039959.00	1546059.00	
104469.00	34369.00	
35392.00	16092.00	
12801.00	7062.00	
18813.00	11068.00	
84114.00	59361.00	
70823.00	12085.00	
76556.00	42473.00	
76375.00	44526.00	
68622.00	34580.00	
73045.00	51901.00	
75711.00	65488.00	
31794.00	25904.00	
51613.00	36994.00	

The analysis is on performance using earned value analysis as presented in table 4. The Planned dates, actual dates, BAC, PV and AV were collected from the SIP office. Those data were used to calculate SV, SVI, CV, CPI, ETC, EAC, VAC and the status of the projects. The overall BAC of the project is NRs 386407.00 thousands. The PV for overall projects as of 25 sep 2020 is NRs 3359124.00 thousands while the EV and AV as of 25 sep 2020 are NRs 1874145.00 thousand and NRs 1832125.00 thousand respectively. As the Actual cost incurred for total project is less than the EV with a positive CV and hence the CPI is more than one (1.02). This indicates that as a whole, the projects are under budget. Since EV is less than the PV, the SV is not positive along with SPI of the project is very less than 1 (0.55). This indicates that the projects under construction as whole are farther behind the schedule and needs immediate action.

The comparative study of the table 4. shows that the cost variance (CV) of all projects positive. Hence Cost performance Index (CPI) for 13 project are more than unity and one project is one. This indicates that all projects are within the budget.

Similarly, all 14 selected projects are negative in SV reflecting need of performance improvement time schedule. The total SV for all projects is equal to NRs (1484979) thousands. For SIP/EMC/ICB-01 only, this value is (-1163600) thousand followed by SIP/CAP/NCB-16 and so on. As such, Schedule performance indexes (SPI) of all projects are less than unity indicating that those projects are behind schedule.

The average index has been calculated as an average of SPI and CPI. The projects having average index less than 0.85 has been considered as a project that needs immediate attention, those projects having index between 1 to 0.85 has been considered as slightly behind Schedule/Budget and the projects within average index one has been considered as the project on track. Following table 4.9, it was found that the 11 projects are needs immediate attention as average index of those projects are less than 0.85. Remaining projects are average index more than 0.85. It is to be noted that through almost all projects are farther behind the Schedule, the average index seems deficient to address each indices closely. Depending upon condition the estimate to complete and estimate at completion may vary from 1.95 million to 3.54 million and 3.78 million to 5.37 million respectively.

Figure 2 Earn Value chart for all project.

All the ongoing fourteen projects indicates that Planned Value in graph above the Earned value and Actual value. It means the project behind the schedule and less work to be done. It shows that progress of work is very slow.

Figure 3 : Earned Value Analysis (S-Curve) of SIP/EMC/ICB-01 (Revised Schedule)

From this graph it can be seen the the detailed calculation of Planed, Earned and Actual Value has 286.7, 152.38 and 149.39 million respectively. From figure 3 it shows that Time variance at 35 month ie, 15.10 month behind the schedule and Schedule variance at 35 month has (-1163.6) million behind . The cost variance was 29.9 million.

S-Curve of Contract SIP/CAP/NCB-04

Figure 4: S-Curve of SIP/CAP/NCB-04

From this it can be seen the the detailed calculation of Planed, Earned and Actual Value has 39.341, 24.10 and 19.30 Lakh respectively. From figure 4 it shows that Time variance at 40 month ie, 17.9 month behind the schedule and Schedule variance at 40 month has 152.4 Lakh behind. Cost Variance has 48.0 lakh.

S-Curve of contract SIP/CAP/NCB-12

Figure 5 : S-curve of contract SIP/CAP/NCB-12

it can be seen the the detailed calculation of Planed, Earned and Actual Value has 11.81, 6.01 and 5.73 Lakh respectively. From figure 5 it shows that Time variance at 28 month ie, 17.5 month behind the schedule and Schedule variance at 28 month has 58.0 Lakh behind.

8. Conclusion

Based on performance evaluation of the ongoing project's under SIP using earned value analysis and S-Curve, It is revealed that all ongoing projects are within the budget but severaly passed through time overrun except one. For the Earned value analysis, the planned value is far more than the earned values for all the projects which shows the slow progress of the work. Furthermore earned value for the project more than actual value of the project which indicates that the projects are within the budget. By Using Earn Value analysis Method and S- curve. It is found that project within budget, the time overrun is server. The average cost variance percengate is 2.24, Cost performance index is 1.02, shows the effectiveness of cost in the project due to low bedding of 86% contracts. Schedule variance percentage is -44.2% , Schedule performance index is 0.55 and average index is 0.785 which was less then 1.0. Depending upon condition the estimate to complete and estimate at completion may vary from 1.95 million to 3.54 million and 3.78 million to 5.37 million respectively.

9. Recommendation

Client should prepare the project well before implementation with proper planning, designing and detail study from the beginning. The client should be followed provision of PPA 2007 and PPR for extension of time in all contracts. SIP should use EVA and S-curve for all the contract for proper monitoring. Conultant should be pre execution prepration of land acquisition, EIA, IEE and planning of project tasks, resource need and resource planning. Contractor should proper planning and management of qualified technical staff and construction material. Conractor should be advance purchase aggrement the probable incidence in order to avoid shortage of construction material. Hope the ammedment of extension of time clause will be significant for managing the time performance.

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